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INVESTIGATION OF COAL BED METHANE POTENTIAL BASED ON INTERGRATED CLEAT ANALYSIS AND COAL QUALITY; CASE STUDY IN MERAPI TIMUR, LAHAT DISTRICT, SOUTH SUMATRA

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ABSTRACT

Nowadays, conventional energy production has decreased, so it is necessary to develop unconventional based exploration, one of which is Coal Bed Methane (CBM). Indonesia has a high potential of CBM, and one of them is located in South Sumatra which has a potential reserve of 183 TCF. CBM is a gas formed during the coalification process and stored in the cleat through a diffusion process from micropore. Cleats are natural fractures in coal seam and act as controllers of permeability values in development of CBM.

The research area is in Merapi Timur, Lahat District, South Sumatra which is included in Muara Enim Formation. The method used in this research is field observation, data sorting, quantitative analysis, and laboratory analysis. Field observations included observations of coal appearance and measuring cleat attributes, such as aperture, spacing, length, and cleat orientation using scanline method.

Coal deposits in the study area have varying thickness of 4-19.5 m. Data from the measurement of cleats are sorted using the box plot method to validate data. Calculation of cleat is used to determine relationship between cleat attributes, interpretation of cleat density and permeability. Quantitative analysis of cleats showed an average aperture of 0.01-0.020 cm and an average spacing of 1.51-6.15 cm. Cleat distribution and orientations indicates two major trends, namely NW-SE and NE-SW. The cleat density for individual seams varies ranged from 0.2-0.36 cm/cm². Permeability based on outcrop data has a range from 10.18 to 108.56 md. The results of laboratory analysis showed rank of coal in the study area categorized as sub-bituminous with a maximum vitrinite reflectance value (%R_v Max) of 0.32-0.45%. Data from results of cleat

analysis and coal quality indicate that the research area has potential for CBM exploration development.

INTRODUCTION

Over time, the community's need for oil and gas has increased significantly, but it is inversely proportional to availability of production and oil and gas reserves that are increasingly depleting. Along with this situation, the development of alternative energy is needed to overcome it. One of the alternative energy potentials that can be developed is Coal Bed Methane (CBM). Based on study of Advanced Resources International, Inc. (ARI), Indonesia has a CBM potential of 450 TCF (Trillion Cubic Feet). CBM as a new energy is expected to be an alternative solution to meet national energy needs. This is quite promising especially in Sumatra and Kalimantan with large CBM reserves and potential. Geological mapping is needed to identify the existence of CBM potential that is feasible and has economic value for exploration. This attracts the writers to raise the topic in research.

Coal Bed Methane (CBM) is methane gas produced during the coalification process and trapped inside coal. Methane gas has lowest caloric content compared to other natural gas and has a single atomic chain resulting in less exhaust gas or smoke. Thus, CBM is considered more environmentally friendly than other gases. In CBM plays, coal acts as the host rock and reservoir rock. Coal generally has very low porosity and matrix permeability. Thus, cleats are needed for the commercial rate of gas to flow from micropore matrix (coal mineral) and microscopic lamination to production wells. Cleats are natural cracks in the coal seam formed due to coal dehydration, local and regional stresses, and overburden loading. Based on type, cleats are divided into two, namely face cleats and butt cleats. According to Muhartanto, A and Iskandar, E (2006),

face cleats are the main fracture pathways or primary cleats that are continuous along the coal seam while the butt cleat is a secondary cleat that is not continuous. The shape of the face cleat is parallel to the maximum direction of compressional stress and perpendicular to the fold axis, while the butt cleat is a fracture release strain whose shape is parallel to the fold axis (CSG, 2012). Understanding the cleat geometry and important orientation for CBM is the pathway for gas flowing from the matrix to the wellbore. Based on ganasha, the formation of coal cleats is divided into two, namely endogenic cleats and exogenic cleats (Ryan, 2003). Endogenic cleats are formed together with the coalification process and experience material loading which results in dewatering and shrinkage processes so as to form fractures that are perpendicular to the coal seam, while exogenic cleats are formed after the formation of endogenic cleats caused by tectonic influences and structures, such as faults and folds. Cleats have an important role in the development of CBM as an indicator of permeability. Connectivity between coal cleats that are closely related can increase the value of permeability. The better relationship between cleats, the higher permeability value and vice versa. The relationship between cleats and permeability influences the determination of CBM.

From what is known, there are two CBM blocks that produce CBM gas, namely Sekayu Block and Rambutan Block. At Sekayu Block, there are five drilling wells and one production well with a depth of 894 ft - 1960 ft. The production well has three coal seams with the drilling method used is a case holes compression and total gas production is 398-59.000 SCF. At Rambutan Block, there has five drilling wells with depths from 2.015 ft-3.140 ft. The drilling methods used are case holes, open holes, and radial jetting. Consist of five seams with a depth of about 30 metres and total gas production of 10,000 SCF. The depth target of CBM in South Sumatra ranges from 810 ft - 3,140 ft (Lemigas, 2012).

The study was conducted in Merapi Timur, Lahat District, South Sumatra. The research area is included in the South Sumatra Basin with amount of CBM reserves reaching 183 TCF (Permana, 2007). This study aims to determine coal permeability, predict potential of CBM, and relationship between cleats and coal rank.

METHODS

The methods used in the study were field observation, data polling, quantitative analysis, laboratory analysis, and interpretation. The literature

study was conducted to determine geological conditions of the study area from previous researchers. Field observations included observations of megascopic coal appearance, sampling, and cleat measurements. Coal observation includes descriptions, position measurements (strike/dip), and thickness. Coal samples were carried out laboratory analysis to determine the maceral content and coal quality. Cleat measurements, such as the aperture, spacing, height, and orientation of the cleat, were carried out using the scanline method (Figure 1). Scanline length is adjusted to the thickness of coal. Cleat measurement data is done using a box plot method to validate data. The results of cleat data validation were analyzed quantitatively to determine the relationship between aperture, spacing, density, and cleat orientation. Calculation of coal permeability uses the equations of Lucia (1983), Scott (1999), and Aguilera (1995) that connect value of coal permeability and quality.

REGIONAL GEOLOGY

South Sumatra Basin has a basement in form of a Pre-Tertiary rock complex consisting of limestone, andesite, breccia, granodiorite, filite, quartzite and granite. Sediment deposition takes place afterwards, i.e. Tertiary deposited is not aligned with the basement. In sequence, the Tertiary formation deposits in this basin start from Lahat Formation, Talang Akar Formation, Baturaja Formation, Gumai Formation, Air Benakat Formation, Muara Enim Formation, and Kasai Formation (Figure 2).

Lahat Formation is deposited in Early Oligocene formed on a terrestrial environment composed of tuffaceous deposits, agglomerates, tuffaceous breccia, andesite, shale, siltstone, sandstone and coal. Subsequent sedimentation took place at same time the sea trough (transgression) and decrease in the basin took place in Late Oligocene-Middle Miocene (Talang Akar Formation-Gumai Formation). Talang Akar Formation is not aligned in Late Oligocene-Early Miocene formed in a fluvial environment-shallow seas are composed of coarse sandstones, sandstone, siltstone and coal. Baturaja Formation is deposited harmoniously during the Early Miocene-Middle Miocene and is formed in a litoral-neritic environment composed of reef limestones, side-grape leaves, and coarse clay or marl. Gumai Formation is deposited in harmony with Early Miocene-Middle Miocene which has a deep sea environment. The next deposition process takes place simultaneously with the process of ocean shrinkage (regression) and change in extensible tectonic phase into compressions takes place in the

Middle Miocene-Pliocene (Kasai Formation). Air Benakat Formation is deposited in harmony with the Middle Miocene-Late Miocene and is formed in a neritic environment - shallow seas arranged by sandstones as the main constituent. Muara Enim Formation is deposited in harmony with the Miocene-Pliocene in environment of fluvial and delta which is composed of sandstones, siltstone, claystone, and coal. Kasai Formation was deposited in harmony in the Late Pliocene-Pleistocene formed in a terrestrial environment with tuff and tuff sandstone lithology. The formation process of this formation was also followed by an increase in volcanic activity along the row of hills so that the volcanic distribution radius increased and became an insertion in several coal seams in the Muara Enim Formation. Subsequent precipitations occur in Quaternaries which are generally the result of a breakdown of previously existing rocks. The research area is in Muara Enim Formation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Administratively, the research area is in Merapi Timur, Lahat District, South Sumatra. Based on the results of field observations, three rock units were found, namely sandstone, siltstone, and claystone (Figure 3). Coal outcrops in the study area were found in claystone units. Claystone acts as an overburden from each layer of coal. Coal in the study area was included in the Muara Enim Formation which was deposited in the Late Miocene-Early Pliocene was deposited during the regression phase. (Ryacudu, 2005).

Coal Quality Analysis

In megascopically, the appearance of coal in the study area shows characteristics that are relatively same as black, dull with bright, brittle, uneven, subchocoidal, and black scratches (Figure 4). The thickness of the coal seams varies between 4.1 m - 19.6 m. The distribution of coal distribution patterns is relatively east-west. Coal sampling was carried out at each observation location to determine the maceral content and coal quality. The results of laboratory analysis showed that the coal in the study area had a maximum value of vitrinite reflectance (% R_v Max) of 0.32-0.45% (Table 1). According to Ward's (1986), coal rank in the study area was categorized as sub-bituminous.

Cleat Attributes Analysis

In addition to coal observations, cleat measurements were also carried out using scanline method in each

location. The scanline length used depends on thickness of each coal. Cleat measurements carried out include the aperture, spacing, height, and orientation of cleat. The location for measuring cleats is in eight locations; which four locations in Banjasari village (A, B, C, D) and four locations in Malawi villages (E, F, G, H) (Figure 5). The number of cleat measurements in each location varies depending on coal thickness, coal characteristics, and local geological structure. The total cleats measured at the study site were 910 cleats. The cleat measurement data is sorted using boxplot method to avoid errors in data collection in field (Figure 6). The data used in quantitative analysis is a value that is between quartile 1 (Q1) and quartile 3 (Q3).

Table 2 and figure 7 showing average aperture ranged from 0.01 to 0.1, with an average of 0.01-0.020 cm. Cleat distance is related to rank, layer thickness, mineral composition and ash content. In general, the distance between cleats will be more tight as coal rank increases. The average cleat distance in sub-bituminous coal 2-15 cm, in volatile bitumen coal is 0.3-2 cm, and volatile bitumen coal is < 1 cm high (Cardott, 2001 in CSG, 2012) Therefore, cleat distance is tighter on coal rich in vitrinite and low ash, and thin coal seams. Distance measurement between cleat. The average distance between cleats in all study locations varied from 1.51-6.15 cm.

Cleat Density

The measurement of cleat density used in this study is total length of cleats in square area divided by the area. Cleat density can be expressed in units of length/area, such as (ft/ft², cm/cm², m/m², and km/km²). Cleat density can affect coal stability and success of cavity stimulation. The relationship between density and cleat attributes is important for understanding origin and development of cleats. Density is related to the geometry and connectivity of cleat networks, where higher density might have good network and connectivity. Average density has been used to understand the relationship with other attributes: average aperture and average spacing. The approach is made to relationship between average density and average distance to avoid errors due to the structure or tectonic influences that occur. The crossplot graph shows trend lines of the legal distribution of strength (Figure 8). The average cleat density of all locations varies between 0.200-0.367 cm/cm². In addition, an analysis of the relationship between average cleat density and average aperture was carried out with an aperture range of 0.01-0.02 cm (Figure 8b).

Orientation Cleat

The orientation of cleat can be used as a reference in conducting exploration, where drilling activities are relatively perpendicular to direction of face cleat. In general, the cleat orientation is parallel to horizontal maximum stress direction or is influenced by regional compressive stress. According to Nelson (2002), cleats can be formed at different periods in the history of coal formation due to various mechanisms such as the effects of dehydration or desiccation, devolatilization, deposition mechanisms, coal seam thickness, maceral content, coal lithotypes, coal degrees, depositional environment, thermal contraction, regional tectonics, geological structures, and mining work activities. The results of data measurement of position of cleats on coal outcrops, analyzed using stereographic projections and rose diagrams. Based on distribution and orientation, there are two general directions in the research location, namely NW - SE and NE - SW (Figure 5). The orientation that has the direction of NW - SE lies in five locations, namely A, D, E, F, and G. The orientation direction of NE - SW is at location B, C and H.

Rotation Cleat

Cleat can be endogenic or exogenic. Endogenic cleats are formed due to changes in coal properties (coalification) associated with changes in the internal pressure system, compaction and drying. Exogenic cleats are formed as a result of external stresses acting on the coal seam including tectonic pressure, changes in fluid pressure, folds and the development of tensile stresses. Exogenic cleats usually have lower permeability. According to Apriyani, et al. (2014), the classification of type of ganessa cleat is influenced by the value of dip. The dip value is 70° - 90° or perpendicular to the coal seam is an endogenic cleat type, while dip is $<70^\circ$ or not perpendicular to the coal seam including the exogenic cleat type. Based on the results of the analysis, it shows that the locations A, B, E, F, and H are exogenic cleat types, while C, D, and G are included in the endogenic type of cleats (Figure 9). Thus, the permeability value of locations C, D, and G is greater than other locations.

Permeability Analysis

Permeability is one of the important parameters for the production of effective and economical coal methane. The presence of abundant cleat can increase permeability in accordance with a high fracture reservoir. In CBM, almost all gas and water

flows occur in fracture and cleat. According to Scott (1999), permeability is influenced by density, aperture, and spacing ranging from Micro Darcys to Darcys. Calculation of permeability from cleat attributes can use Scott's equation (1999), Lucia (1983) or Aguilera (1995). In this study, the calculation of permeability using the Aguilera equation (1995). Aguilera (1995) combines the relationship of permeability with Darcys's law:

$$K_f = 8.35 \times 10^6 W^2 \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

$$\text{Cubes, } K_2 = (2/3) (K_f W^2 / Z) \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

$$\text{Match Sticks, } K_2 = (1/2) (K_f W^2 / Z) \dots\dots (3)$$

Where, K = permeability (Darcys), W = aperture (cm), and Z = spacing (cm).

Statistical analysis based on coal outcrop data with this equation has permeability values ranging between 13.57-144.753 md (cubes) and 10.18-108.56 md (match sticks) as seen in Table 4. Increasing the value of permeability is influenced by disappearance of overburden pressure, while the presence of fillers in the cleat results in a decrease in the value of permeability. Based on the results of the cleat permeability in the study area it can be analogous to the San Juan Basin and the Black Warrior Basin, USA (Figure 10). In generally, good coal for prospect cbm have permeability range from 30-50 md (Lemigas, 2012). Thus, based on the permeability value of coal in the research area it is classified as good and has the potential to be carried out in development of CBM.

Relationship Coal Rank on Cleat Development

Cleat on coal can be formed through two processes, exogenic and endogenic. In the exogenic process, which influences the development of cleats, it is the coalification process which will later affect the coal rank produced. While in exogenic processes, the external pressure process due to tectonic forces is the forming factor, which in turn increases the quality of the coal rank. Then the higher a coal rank on coal, the higher the level of development of cleats in the coal. The level of development of this cleat will later provide a value that is directly proportional to the potential of CBM.

CONCLUSION

1. Coal in the study area has a thickness varying from 4.1-19.6 m.
2. Based on results of laboratory analysis, rank coal in the study area was categorized as sub-bituminous (Ward 1986).

3. Quantitative analysis shows an average aperture of 0.01-0.02 cm, spacing of 1.51-6.15 cm, and cleat density of 0.200-0.367 cm / cm².
4. Cleat attribute analysis shows a directly proportional relationship between cleat density and distance, and the relationship between cleat and aperture density.
5. The distribution and orientation of cleats in the study area shows three directions, namely NW-SE dan NE-SW.
6. Based on rotation analysis of cleat, the type of cleats that develop in the study area are endogenic and exogenic.
7. The permeability value of the coal cleats of the study area ranges from 10.18-108.56 md.
8. The research area has the potential to develop Coal Bed Methane (GMB) exploration.

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TABLE 1

RESULT OF MUARA ENIM FORMATION COAL MACERAL ANALYSIS IN RESEARCH AREA

Table 1. Result of Muara Enim Formation coal maceral analysis in the research area.

No	No Sample	Lithology	Mean Reflectance Vitrinite (% Rv random)	Range (%)	Standard Deviation	N	Maceral Composition (%)								Mineral Matter (%)	
							V		I			L				Pyrite
							D	T	S	F	Sc	I	R	Su		
1	4261/16	BB	0.37	0.34-0.40	0.01	100	67	4	3.4	6	3.6	1.6	4.4	1.4	7.6	
2	4262/16	BB	0.33	0.30-0.38	0.01	100	67.4	5	4.6	5	2.4	-	1.6	-	11	
3	4263/16	BB	0.39	0.35-0.45	0.02	100	64	4	4	6	4.4	-	3.6	1.6	8	
4	4264/16	BB	0.27	0.23-0.32	0.02	100	83	-	5	5.6	1.6	2.4	-	1	1.4	
5	4265/16	BB	0.27	0.24-0.34	0.02	100	70	2.4	4	10	3	2.6	1	-	7	
6	4266/16	BB	0.31	0.27-0.34	0.02	100	50.4	2.4	11	9.6	3	4.6	1.6	0.6	8.4	
7	4267/16	BB	0.36	0.32-0.40	0.02	100	75	3	2	7.4	3.4	0.6	1.6	1	6	
8	4268/16	BB	0.32	0.30-0.36	0.02	100	72	2.4	3.4	3.6	2	-	-	3.6	12	

Note : BB = Coal
 SHC = Shaly coal
 CSH = Coaly shale
 CS = Carbonaceous shale
 SH = Shale
 N = Number of measurement

V = Vitrinite
 I = Inertinite
 L = Liptinite
 D = Desmocollinite
 T = Telecollinite
 S = Semifusinite

F = Fusinite
 Sc = Sclerotinite
 I = Inertodetrinite
 R = Resinite
 S = Suberinite
 Pyrite = pyrite

TABLE 2

(A) COAL RANK CLASSIFICATION BASED ON VITRINITE REFLECTANCE MAXIMUM (WARD 1986), (B) COAL RANK IN RESEARCH AREA CATEGORIZED AS SUB-BITUMINOUS

Rank	Maximum Reflectance (%Rv Max)
Sub-Bituminous	< 0.47
High Volatile Bituminous C	0.47 - 0.51
High Volatile Bituminous B	0.51 - 0.71
High Volatile Bituminous A	0.71 - 0.10
Medium Volatile Bituminous	0.10 - 1.50
Low Volatile Bituminous	1.50 - 2.05
Semi -Antrachite	2.05 - 3 (approx)
Antrachite	> 3.00

(a)

No	No Sample	Maximum Reflectance (%Rv Max)	Coal Rank
1	4261/18	0.40	Sub - Bituminous
2	4262/18	0.38	Sub - Bituminous
3	4263/18	0.45	Sub - Bituminous
4	4264/18	0.32	Sub - Bituminous
5	4265/18	0.34	Sub - Bituminous
6	4266/18	0.34	Sub - Bituminous
7	4267/18	0.40	Sub - Bituminous
8	4268/18	0.36	Sub - Bituminous

(b)

TABLE 3**QUANTITATIVE ANALYSIS BASED ON SCANLINE DATA**

Location	Average aperture (cm)	Average spacing (cm)	Average density (cm/cm ²)
A	0.010	4.10	0.367
B	0.010	1.51	0.200
C	0.020	6.15	0.360
D	0.015	2.20	0.272
E	0.013	2.36	0.266
F	0.010	1.83	0.222
G	0.016	2.82	0.327
H	0.012	2.20	0.255

TABLE 4**RESULT OF PERMEABILITY ANALYSIS IN RESEARCH AREA**

Location	Average aperture (cm)	Average spacing (cm)	Cleat Permeability (mildarcys)	
			Cubes	Match Sticks
A	0.010	4.102	13.571	10.18
B	0.010	1.511	36.841	27.63
C	0.020	6.153	144.753	108.56
D	0.015	2.202	127.980	95.99
E	0.013	2.364	66.037	49.53
F	0.010	1.835	30.338	22.75
G	0.016	2.828	133.403	100.05
H	0.012	2.205	52.349	39.26

Figure 1 – Schematic diagram showing the cleat/fracture attributes that were measured (Sapiie, et al, 2014).

Figure 2 – Regional Stratigraphy of South Sumatera Basin (Ryacudu, 2005).

Figure 3 – Coal distribution map in research arca showing four coal seam (A, B, C, and D).

Figure 4 – Sample coal outcrops in research area (location a, b, c, and d).

Figure 5 – Cleat observation map in research area.

Box Plot Aperture

Variable	Count	Mean	Minimum	Lower whisker	Q1	Median	Q3	Upper whisker	Maximum
E	131	0.0227	0.0100	0.0100	0.0100	0.0100	0.0200	0.0300	0.2500
F	80	0.0124	0.0100	0.0100	0.0100	0.0100	0.0100	0.0100	0.0700
G	146	0.0253	0.0100	0.0100	0.0100	0.0200	0.0300	0.0600	0.1200

Box Plot Spacing

Variable	Count	Mean	Minimum	Lower whisker	Q1	Median	Q3	Upper whisker	Maximum
E	131	3.0229	0.5000	0.5000	1.5000	2.4000	3.4000	6.2000	22.2000
F	80	1.9931	0.6000	0.6000	1.2000	1.9000	2.5500	4.0000	4.0000
G	147	4.0184	0.4000	0.4000	1.5000	3.0000	5.0000	10.0000	19.5000

Figure 6 – Validation the attribute data using boxplot method.

Figure 7 – (a) Average aperture on each location, (b) average spacing on each location, (c) average density on each location.

Figure 8 – (a) Chart of average spacing versus average density with a power law trend line, (b) Chart showing the crossplots between average aperture and average density from all scanline locations.

Figure 9 – Rotation cleat on each location.

Figure 10 – Comparison of coal permeability in the research area with other basins in the world.